

Acidified Alum Sludge and Fly-ash as Adjunct to Coagulation

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Alum-sludge (aging less than one hour) and fly-ash (aggregate less than 100 mesh) after treatment with sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid separately could be used as adjuncts to coagulation in Municipal Water treatment. Those were found to be efficient in reducing the actual alum requirement. Sulphuric acid treated sludge was proved to be most effective adjunct, specially in the higher turbidity range. These also possessed the capability of diminishing the coliform count in supply water and initiated flocculation of both phyto and zooplanktons usually present in river water.

ATTEMPTS were made from time to time for the better clarification of turbid water with the aid of polyelectrolytes¹⁻⁵ and also with the aid of inert coprecipitants⁶⁻¹¹. Alum-sludge treated with sulphuric acid, termed as 'Reclaimed sludge'¹²⁻¹⁶ was also found suitable for the same purpose. Reports are available in support of removal of bacteria by lime-sludge, alum-flocs¹⁷, fly-ash¹⁰ etc. and of flocculation of algae by both mineral coagulants¹⁸ and synthetic organic polyelectrolytes¹⁹⁻²². The object of the present study is to investigate the possibility of utilising acidified alum-sludge and acidified fly-ash as adjuncts to coagulation of river water and their capability to reduce coliform bacterial count and algae population in the usual alum coagulation process.

Materials and Methods

Water samples were collected from a fixed depth of the Ganges basin near Palta Water Works (PWW), Barrackpore. Sample of alum-sludge from the sludgevat of PWW was selected depending on the settleability rate: the chosen sample was 'consolidated'¹⁵ within 30 mins. i.e., a number of samples were taken in tall one-litre cylinders and allowed to coagulate after initial shaking to find out the optimum time for total settlement of floc-particles. Less than 1 hr. aged¹⁶ samples were separately treated with 0.02N H₂SO₄ and 0.02 N H₃PO₄ at pH 3.0-3.5 and was centrifuged. These regenerated sludge were made free of acid by repeated washings.

Samples of fly-ash from the boiler plant of Palta Water Works were collected and sieved through 100 mesh. Sieved samples were treated with 0.02 N H₂SO₄ and with 0.02 N H₃PO₄ separately at pH 3.0-3.5. Acidified samples were made completely free of acid by repeated washings and then air-dried. 0.02 N H₂SO₄-treated samples are termed as 'sulphated' and that treated with 0.02 N H₃PO₄ are termed as 'phosphated' ash samples.

Turbidity of water samples was measured by Jackson's candle turbidimeter and all related physico-

chemical characteristics were determined by standard procedure²³. To fix up alum doses for limiting coagulation (below 5 p.p.m. of turbidity in SiO₂ scale as prescribed by W.H.O. and ICMR), the laboratory study consisted of a series of 'Jar Tests'²⁴, the variables were examined to standardise the procedure²⁵. In each case floc size, settling characteristics and temperature of the system were recorded to check the reproducibility of the results.

Bacterial populations in the treated and untreated water were compared by 'Presumptive coliform count'²⁶ (Ministry of Health, London) and enumeration of algae was done as usual.²⁷

Results and Discussion

To ascertain the influence of reclaimed sludge and acidified ash as adjuncts to coagulation of river water, a comparative determination of actual alum requirement (2nd column of Table 2) and that when used along with (a) sulphated and (b) phosphated sludge, and (c) sulphated and (d) phosphated ash (3rd to 6th columns respectively) were performed. The partial chemical analysis of water sample used in this investigation is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—AVERAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF RIVER WATER MUDS UNDER INVESTIGATION. AVERAGE OF 52 SAMPLES OF DIFFERENT SEASONS

	Range (p.p.m.)
Total solids	1000 to 100
Suspended solids	850 to 100
Calcium Ion (in CaCO ₃ scale)	120 to 40
Magnesium ion (in CaCO ₃ scale)	50 to 20
Bicarbonate ion (in CaCO ₃ scale)	280 to 50
Chloride ion (in Cl scale)	250 to 10
Total Hardness (in CaCO ₃ scale)	300 to 80
pH	8.10 to 7.80
Conductance (in μ mho/cm)	150 to 180
Temperature (in °C)	32.50 to 29.0

N.B. River water samples were collected at different seasons of the year to maintain universality of the finding as far as practicable.

The raw sludge used was of the following quality : Solid content per ml : 0.2605 g; pH : 7.60; Exchangeable Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Fe^{++} : 35, 25, 10.50 p.p.m. respectively (in average); salinity (in Cl scale) : 12 p.p.m. and alkalinity (in CaCO_3 scale) : 75 p.p.m.

alum) and the adjuncts (acidified sludge/ash) is also a determining factor. In this study it was noticed that sludge suspension should be poured 60 secs after the addition of alum whereas ash to be introduced 120 secs before addition of alum and to be uniformly

TABLE 2—SAVING OBTAINED WITH (A) ALUM+SULPHATED SLUDGE, (B) ALUM+PHOSPHATED SLUDGE, (C) ALUM+SULPHATED ASH, (D) ALUM+PHOSPHATED ASH

Sample	Alum treatment		(a) Alum+ Sulphated Sludge	(b) Alum+ Phosphated Sludge	(c) Alum+ Sulphated ash	(d) Alum+ Phosphated ash
	Doses g/gal.	in lbs/m.gal	Dose in g/gal.	Dose in g/gal.	Dose in g/gal.	Dose in g/gal.
	0.90	128.57	0.75	0.85	0.85	0.80
ii	1.00	142.85	0.70	0.80	0.90	0.80
iii	1.20	171.42	0.80	0.90	1.00	0.85
iv	1.10	157.13	0.65	0.75	0.90	0.75
v	1.20	171.42	0.70	0.80	0.90	0.75
vi	1.60	228.56	1.15	1.30	1.30	1.20
vii	1.65	235.70	0.95	1.00	1.20	1.00
viii	1.70	242.84	0.95	1.20	1.30	1.10
ix	1.80	257.14	1.00	1.15	1.35	1.20
x	1.40	199.98	0.80	0.90	0.95	0.90
xi	2.00	285.70	1.00	1.10	1.20	1.05
xii	2.20	314.26	1.20	1.35	1.45	1.30
xiii	1.90	271.42	1.00	1.15	1.30	1.20
xiv	1.85	264.27	1.10	1.30	1.45	1.30

N.B. : Assumption : i) 36 million gallon of water (turbid) requires 9 metric ton of basic alum containing 17.5% Al_2O_3 , 0.5% Fe_2O_3 , no As_2O_3 .

Abbreviations : g/gal. lbs/m.gal, mean grains per gallon pounds per million gallon respectively.

Air-dried sludge contained Al_2O_3 : 30.60%, Fe_2O_3 : 6.10%, CaO : 4.20%, MgO : 3.40%; while the oven-dried sludge contained 42.90% of Al_2O_3 .

The high ferric oxide content of sludge was due to waste from local iron-works.

Analysis of fly-ash (dried) showed pH : 8.10 (1 g in 10 ml. water); its available Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Fe^{++} (mg. per 100 g ash) in 1 N NH_4Cl aq. extract : 16.60, 2.80, 0.51 respectively.

Salinity : 20 mg and alkalinity : 160 mg (both in aqueous suspension in mg. per 100 g ash in the usual scale; density (soaked in water) : 1.436 g/ml; aggregate : less than 100 mesh.

The nature of settling with the use of acidified ash and sludge, actually varied from very poor to much satisfactory in case of water of high turbidity (i.e., more than 800 p.p.m.). The decrease in alum requirement when used along with these adjuncts for coagulation was almost insignificant at lower level of turbidity (i.e., below 300 p.p.m.). It is worth-mentioning that increased concentration of adjuncts over the optimum dosage in the present study actually inhibited coagulation due to the phenomenon of 'Charge Reversal'²⁸ of clay-Al-adjunct myceli. The order of the application of primary coagulant (i.e.,

mixed with the stirrer (of r.p.m. 200) of the 'Jar Test apparatus' followed by the coagulant-application and reduction of stirrer motion to 20 r.p.m. It was suggested^{10,25} that a part of ash assisted floc formation and the rest helped to increase the size of floc due to adsorption on the precipitate^{10,25}. Coprecipitation with sludge and ash lent an additional support from the views of Francirek²⁹. In case of coagulation by sludge it was predicted by Albrect¹¹ that the mechanism of coagulation is the same as that with ash. Acidified sludge contained in addition to soluble $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, other allied compounds viz., oxychlorides and oxysulphates and these possessed superior coagulating characteristics¹⁴. Iwase³⁰ opined that the sulphate ion was more efficient than phosphate one in shifting the hydrolysis of Al^{3+} . The present study revealed that the sulphated sludge was more effective than phosphated one and thus supports the idea put forward by Iwase³⁰. Greater coagulating character of phosphated ash in conjunction to sulphated one could be explained with the help of Valency Rule³¹. It has been noted (to be published elsewhere) that sodium aluminate is more efficient than alum in coagulation of red water because of ready formation of hydrated alumina polymeric³² (since the pH of aluminate is higher than alum). The addition of sludge and ash did not have any disadvantageous effect on total dissolved

solids, sludge volume, pH, salinity and alkalinity of water. Thus a typical sample of river water (turbidity 1800 p.p.m.) when treated with alum alone and when along with adjuncts like (a), (b), (c), (d) produced the sludge-volume 1.80, 2.10, 2.15, 2.30 ml. respectively.

To study the disinfecting effect (vide Table 3) of acidified sludge/ash, MPN was counted when used along with adjunct and when alum alone. It was found that no beneficial effect could be achieved when alum was used along with acidified adjunct in comparison to alum with raw adjunct.¹⁰

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF ALUM ALONE AND (A), (B), (C), (D) TREATMENT ON BACTERIA COUNT (MPN)

Sample No.	River water MPN per 100 ml	Bacterial count per 100 ml. of treated water				
		only alum treatment	(a) treatment + alum	(b) treatment + alum	(c) treatment + alum	(d) treatment + alum
I	10,000	110	50	80	80	80
II	16,000	250	110	120	110	130
III	12,000	225	111	80	80	120
IV	6,000	900	350	450	450	450
V	45,000	16,000	500	900	900	900
VI	9,000	900	80	50	50	50
VII	35,000	900	450	450	600	600

Average of 20 Samples were taken in each sample : each figure of MPN is assigned to Mode of the series.

Comparative enumeration of algae population in unreacted water, as well as in alum treated and (alum+adjunct) treated water revealed (c.f. Table 4)

TABLE 4—COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF ALUM AND ALUM PLUS TREATMENT*— (A), (B), (C), (D) ON ALGAL COUNT : WATER SAMPLES WERE TAKEN FROM THE SETTLING TANK OF SLOW SAND FILTRATION SYSTEM OF PALTA WATER WORKS, BARRACKPORE.

Sample No.	Turbidity in p.p.m. (units)	Original algal count No. of cells in water per ml	Alum reqd. alone and with aids (a), (b), (c), (d), for complete removal of algae due to flocculation				
			Alum alone in g/gal.	Alum+(a) in g/gal.	Alum+(b) g/gal.	Alum+(c) in g/gal.	Alum+(d) in g/gal.
1	65	3420	16.50	12.00	13.00	10.50	11.00
2	35	1780	10.00	9.00	9.50	8.00	9.00
3	25	4720	7.00	6.50	6.50	5.00	6.00
4	50	2240	14.00	13.00	13.00	12.50	12.50
5	50	3480	15.50	14.00	14.50	13.00	14.00

Total algal population in water sample from settling tank comprises mainly of Melosira, Navicula, Eudorina, Monas, Oscillatoria, Nostoc, Cymbella, Synedra, Fragilaria, Scytonera etc.

* (a) = sulphated sludge, (b) = phosphated sludge, (c) = sulphated ash, (d) = phosphated ash.

that aggregation of discrete algae cells were better in presence of adjunct which helped to subside the free suspension (almost 100% in each of adjunct treatments). The removal of bacteria was better with acidified sludge in comparison to acidified ash as shown in Table 3 and better than raw adjunct³³.

Such difference in capacity to remove micro-organisms is possibly due to 3-dimensional matrix of algae-adjunct formation as shown by Tenney²⁰⁻²¹ in case of algae-polyelectrolyte system.

Sulphated sludge and phosphated ash reduced the time of settlement and floc formation by 33% and 50% approximately, thus in case of a typical sample of turbidity 1200 p.p.m. the time for first floc formation with alum alone was 180 secs and the complete floc formation required 300 secs; whereas with sulphated sludge and phosphated ash (used separately)+alum, the time was 90 secs and 120 secs. respectively. The application of these adjuncts minimises the disposal problem, reduces the capital cost for chemical treatment. The cost of chlorination of final effluent for disinfection and for algicidal application in raw water as a protection against chokeage of filter beds is also reduced.

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